

From Heat to the Heart: Investigating the Love Behind the Law from Science to Scripture

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Abstract

This paper argues that laws – whether legal, scientific, or scriptural – are best understood as abstractions of deeper truths rather than rigid rules. Legal codes approximate the management of social behavior, while scientific laws describe physical realities within the limits of explicit assumptions. In a similar way, scriptural laws are not absolute prescriptions, but are guidelines pointing toward the foundational principle of love. Read this way, the Bible can be reimagined not as a rule book, but as a love story that invites deeper reflection on how to love more fully. To develop this claim, we begin with heat conduction in materials, showing how scientific governing laws shift with scale and context. We then turn to scripture, highlighting moments where a deeper moral reality is revealed “behind” the law. Building on this foundation, we offer perspectives on Black Liberation, Womanist/Feminist, and Queer theologies, before closing with reflections on the practical implications for everyday life.

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Introduction

What if the deepest truth behind all laws – legal, scriptural, and even scientific – is the single principle of love? To answer this question, we must first understand what a law actually is.

In his discussion of jurisprudence, legal scholar Willis defined law as a scheme of social control (Willis 1926), suggesting that laws are necessary to protect social interests that society has deemed worthy of protection. That is, laws are tools for managing interactions between individuals, with “society” defined as a group of people with a set of common interests. What happens, then, if these laws are not followed? Can we define a “crime” as an action in opposition to, or in defiance of the law? In their work “What is a Crime?” (Lamond 2007), Lamond suggests that classifying an action as a crime goes beyond the action itself, but the intention behind it – defining crime as anything that undermines our confidence that others will act in socially justifiable ways. That is, crimes cause others to consider abandoning their own socially acceptable behavior in self-defense, or self-preservation.

Exodus 20:13 (KJV)

“Thou shalt not kill.”

According to the United States Federal Legal Code, murder is defined as the “*unlawful killing of a human being with malice aforethought*” (“18 USC 1111: Murder” 2025), while manslaughter is defined as “*the unlawful killing of a human being without malice*” (“18 USC 1112: Manslaughter” 2025). Both of these actions are considered crimes under the law because they undermine the general societal confidence that a person can go about their regular business and keep their life. In the case of murder, it reduces the assurance that others will not *intentionally* attempt to kill them,

and in the case of manslaughter, it erodes trust that others will act reasonably in the heat of passion (voluntary manslaughter) or act responsibly to prevent death (involuntary manslaughter). For example, after learning about a drunk driver killing an innocent person in a car accident, I might begin to drive my car with the expectation that a drunk driver might kill me as well. This could potentially result in a situation where I interpret the slightest bit of imperfection from other drivers as a situation where I might die, causing me to drive irrationally as well – creating a feedback loop where all drivers on the road no longer have faith that others are driving in accordance with road safety laws, thereby causing a breakdown of order due to individual attempts at self-preservation. Following this argument, self-preservation could be said to be induced by a *fear* of being killed.

In legal studies, this separation of action (*actus reus*) from intention (*mens rea*) has enabled systems to differentiate a crime, which consists of both components (LaFave 2017), from other situations with no mental component. For example, unlike murder and manslaughter, which are both considered crimes, a “wrongful death” is considered a civil infraction. That is, a wrongful death of an individual is deemed an outcome that should not have happened, possibly eliciting sympathy from other members of society, but it does not create social volatility. In other words, although someone (or their estate, a company, system, etc.) may be held liable for the death that occurred, the situation does not encourage other members of society to abandon socially acceptable behavior. An example of this is a killing by an insane person – the person (or their estate) will not be held criminally liable, but may still be held civilly liable (*Polmatier v. Russ* 1988), and members of society generally do not fear being killed, as the large majority of people they interact with while going about their business appear to be mentally stable.

Still, beneath this layer, there are situations where the act of killing results in no legal consequences at all for the killer! For example, self-defense is considered a justifiable form of killing under the law (*Brown v. United States* 1921). Tying this discussion to the earlier biblical quote, can we then say that the law “thou shall not kill” is merely an abstraction of a deeper truth? If we consider death to be a bad thing, this law found in The Ten Commandments could be viewed as a surface-level abstraction intended to prevent people from causing the death other people. Through our discussion of crime vs civil liability vs self-defense, we see that the act of causing death (killing) is not as straightforward as it seems, and so the abstraction presented in the Sixth Commandment could be viewed as a guideline, pending the revelation of the truth behind the law – which legal scholars continue to discuss and debate, such as in ongoing conversations surrounding the death penalty (Ichinose 2017).

However, this raises an important question – why do we consider a person causing the death of another person a bad thing? Or rather, is it *always* a bad thing? Some consider medically assisted suicide, an intentional form of killing, a merciful action! If some forms of killing are considered bad and some can be considered good, what differentiates them?

Matthew 22:37–40 (NKJV)

*Jesus said to him, “‘You shall love the Lord your God with all your heart, with all your soul, and with all your mind.’ This is the first and great commandment. And the second is like it: ‘You shall love your neighbor as yourself.’ **On these two commandments hang all the Law and the Prophets.**”*

According to the book of Matthew, when Jesus Christ was asked what the greatest commandments are, He responded that all laws are abstractions of a deeper truth: love. Love for God, and love for “your neighbor”, with contemporary understandings generally in agreement that “neighbor” refers to your fellow human, or any other individual apart from the “self”. However, even with this knowledge of the truth behind all laws, society has still not reached a state of utopia, and I believe this is because love is a term that is hard to define, and harder to implement. In Sternberg’s *Triangular Theory of Love*, they argued that love is made up of three main components: intimacy, passion, and commitment (Sternberg 1986). In *The Art of Loving*, love is described as both a feeling and practice of active concern for the life and growth of another person (Fromm 1956). From a psychological perspective, Alfred Adler argued that all humans are innately wired to seek “belonging” or “social interest” (Adler 1956), aligning with Willis’ definition of the purpose of laws. This psychological perspective forms the basis of modern cognitive theories (Watts and Critelli 1997), and in a study by Fordham et al., therapeutic interventions based on these theories were scientifically and statistically proven to work across any condition, population or context (Fordham et al. 2021). In my previous work, *You Are Not Your Mistakes*, I argued that this “social interest” Adler suggested all humans are programmed to seek out is an abstraction of something deeper: love (Odufisan 2025).

Romans 2:14–15 (NKJV)

*for when Gentiles, who do not have the law, **by nature** do the things in the law, these, although not having the law, are a law to themselves, who show the work of the law written in their hearts, their conscience also bearing witness, and between themselves their thoughts accusing or else excusing them*

In the letter from the apostle Paul to the Romans, he wrote that the “Gentiles”, i.e. all non-Jewish people, *naturally* “do the things in the law” – thousands of years before Adler came up with his psychological theory. Paul stated that the “law is written in our hearts”, suggesting that it is natural for humans to want to love. I believe this is why he insisted in later letters that blind adherence to laws (and not the Spirit behind them) is in direct opposition to love:

2 Corinthians 3:6 (NKJV)

*who also made us sufficient as ministers of the new covenant, not of the letter but of the Spirit;
for the letter kills, but the Spirit gives life.*

In my previous work, I argued that our survival instincts and conscious attempts at self-preservation, which are rooted in fear, are the only things getting in the way of us acting fully in alignment with our natural propensity to love (Odufisan 2025), drawing on the words of Jesus Christ, who succinctly stated this thousands of years ago:

Matthew 16:25 (NKJV)

*For whoever desires to save his life will lose it, but whoever loses his life for My (love's) sake
will find it.*

Recall that scripturally, Jesus is considered the human incarnation of Love, being God in the flesh, since God is defined in the Bible the very concept of Love itself:

1 John 4:8 (NKJV)

He who does not love does not know God, for God is love.

Repeated again a few verses later:

1 John 4:16 (NKJV)

And we have known and believed the love that God has for us. God is love, and he who abides in love abides in God, and God in him.

This idea of love being the deeper truth behind all laws in scripture will be investigated in detail in this work. To demonstrate how this principle of abstraction extends beyond the legal and scriptural realms, we will first investigate scientific laws, where a similar pattern emerges. Specifically, to motivate following sections, Fourier's Law, which governs heat conduction in materials at the macroscale, will be discussed, demonstrating how it really is an abstraction of some deeper scientific principles. Next, we will review some biblical case studies where the love behind the law is revealed, motivating discussions on modern topics in Black Liberation, Feminist/Womanist, and Queer theology. The rest of this work will then discuss the implications of this in everyday life.

Conceptual Framework: Scientific Laws as Abstractions

This section is intended to introduce the conceptual framework used throughout this work – laws, theories, rules, etc. can be viewed as abstractions of deeper realities. For this purpose, we will explore the conduction of heat in materials, starting from the macroscopic Fourier’s Law to the layers beneath, describing how each layer of mathematical equations is a context-dependent approximation of an underlying truth.

The Fourier Heat Equation

Heat conduction in solids largely follows Fourier’s Law, also known as the Heat Equation, given as:

$$\mathbf{q} = -\kappa\nabla T$$

In words, this equation says that the rate of heat flow across a distance, \mathbf{q} , (called the “heat flux”) is directly proportional to how the temperature, T , changes across that same distance. In the equation above, the term κ is the proportionality constant between the heat flow and temperature change and is known as the thermal conductivity. In general, materials with higher thermal conductivities (e.g., metals) transfer heat more efficiently – which is why the handle of a metal spoon becomes hot much faster than the handle of a plastic one. The direction of heat flow is always from hot to cold – even when one feels cold in the winter, it is due to their body losing heat to its surroundings.

Figure 1: Heat Conduction in 1 Dimension

The explanation of Fourier’s Law – that the rate of heat flow is linearly proportional to the rate of temperature change – sounds intuitive, even obvious, as it explains heat transfer in most physically observable applications – “when heat flows to something it gets hotter”. However, describing observable phenomena with mathematical equations requires precision, and as we will show in the next section, Fourier’s Law rests on a set of assumptions that break down under certain conditions.

The Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE)

The Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE) was originally intended to describe the motion of molecules of gases/fluids at the microscopic scale. To motivate this discussion, let us consider how the smell that emanates from cooking a meal spreads. The smell will be stronger the closer one is to the source of the smell, that is, the pot where the food is being cooked, and weaker the further one moves away from the pot. However, if left long enough, and the windows in the kitchen are closed, every location in the kitchen might seem to smell equally strong after some time has passed

– showing that the concentration of a smell can evolve with time. To characterize this “smell”, we can define something called a “distribution function”[†], that is:

$$f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{c}, t)$$

This definition encapsulates the distribution of the smell in the function f , and it is a function of the *position* of the person perceiving the smell, \mathbf{r} , the *velocity* of the gas carrying the smell (velocity is the speed at which the smell spreads with the direction of spread taken into account), \mathbf{c} , and the *time* at which the person smells it, t , since we established that the smell gets stronger in different locations as time progresses. The BTE is then defined thus:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial f}{\partial t}}_{\text{time evolution of } f} + \underbrace{\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} f}_{\text{real space streaming}} + \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{F}}{m} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{c}} f}_{\text{momentum space streaming}} = \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t}\right)_{\text{coll}}}_{\text{collisions}} + \underbrace{S(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{c}, t)}_{\text{source}}$$

The first term on the left-hand side (LHS), a partial derivative of f with respect to time, t , describes how the concentration of the smell at any given position evolves with time.

The next term on the LHS, the “real space streaming” term, describes how the velocity (which is the directionally-aware speed at which the gas moves) influences the concentration of the smell at any given point.

[†] To be even more precise, the “distribution function” captures the probability of finding a molecule of gas with velocity \mathbf{c} at position \mathbf{r} at time t . The concentration of the smell is used here as an analog for the gas particle density.

The last term on the LHS, the “momentum space streaming” term, accounts for the influence of external forces that accelerate the gas particles, changing their velocity. For example, if a fan were blowing in the kitchen, the force from the fan would accelerate the gas molecules carrying the smell in a specific direction. This term also encompasses other forces like gravity.

The first term on the RHS, often called the “collision operator”, represents how collisions redistribute the density of gas particles carrying the smell, and is sometimes written stylistically as Ω_{coll} . It describes any event that causes the gas carrying the smell to change direction. For example, in a closed kitchen, the gas carrying the smell will “bounce” off the walls of the kitchen, by “colliding” with the wall. This term also accounts for particles of gas carrying the smell bumping against each other.

Lastly, on the RHS we also have a source term, which describes whether new gas particles are added to the system or not. In this analogy, the cooking pot is the source of the gas carrying the smell, and if it is sealed shut after a period of time, that influences how the smell spreads – hence the inclusion of a source term in the BTE.

Connection to Heat Conduction

Now we shall discuss the connection of the general BTE to heat conduction. Previously, we captured the mechanism of heat conduction in the Fourier Heat Equation. However, if we zoom in to smaller length scales, it is understood that heat is caused by transmission of energy through atomic vibrations, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Heat Flow through Atomic Vibrations

From quantum mechanics, it is understood that the energy causing these vibrations comes in discrete packets, or “quanta” of energy called phonons. The more phonons are available in a vibrational mode, the stronger the vibration (due to more energy), and consequently, the more heat is being conducted.

A “vibrational mode” is characterized by two types of “frequencies” (with the word “frequency” defined as how often something happens):

- The temporal frequency, ω , which describes how fast the atoms oscillate in time
- The spatial frequency, \mathbf{k} , also known as the wave vector, describes how often the vibration pattern repeats in space across the lattice and which direction it propagates.

Together, \mathbf{k} and ω define the characteristics of a lattice vibration. Figure 3 illustrates temporal frequency, ω , and the spatial frequency, \mathbf{k} , can be understood in direct analogy with the oscillations repeating in space rather than in time.

Figure 3: Frequency vs Amplitude

In general, the relationship between all possible wavevectors and frequencies in a material is called the “dispersion relation”. Broadly speaking, the lowest ω modes (the ones that oscillate slowest in time) are grouped into something called the “acoustic branch”, while higher ω modes are grouped into “optical branches”. This categorization of modes into branches is necessary because it is possible to have multiple modes with the same spatial frequency but different temporal frequencies. Figure 4 illustrates the dispersion relation for a 1-Dimensional chain of two different types of atoms (diatomic chain), showing a plot of all possible vibrational modes.[‡]

[‡] The number of branches in a dispersion relation depends on how many different types of atoms repeat in the structure – the math just works out that way. For example, if there is only one type of atom repeating (a simple “monoatomic” chain), there is just one branch, which is acoustic. If there are two different atom types repeating (a diatomic chain), there are two branches: one acoustic and one optical. For more complex cases with three or more atom types repeating, there will still only be one acoustic branch (i.e. the lowest frequency vibrations), but there will be multiple optical branches in addition.

Figure 4: Dispersion Relation for 1-Dimensional Diatomic Chain of Atoms

At the microscopic scale, heat conduction through a material can then be abstracted by several vibrational modes propagating, colliding with each other, etc. to transfer heat energy across the material. Since phonons are the discrete packets of energy that make these vibrational modes possible, any event that causes these waves to change direction or transfer a phonon from one mode to another is called a “phonon scattering” event. Figure 5 shows two different types of phonon scattering events, with phonon-phonon scattering occurring when two different vibrational modes interact with each other, and phonon-boundary scattering occurring as the lattice wave hits the boundary of the material, an interface with another material, etc.

Figure 5: Phonon Scattering Events

The BTE can then be expressed in a slightly modified form to capture the distribution and propagation of these vibrations:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial n_{\mathbf{k},p}}{\partial t}}_{\text{time evolution}} + \underbrace{v_{\mathbf{k},p} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} n_{\mathbf{k},p}}_{\text{real space streaming}} = \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial n_{\mathbf{k},p}}{\partial t} \right)_{\text{coll}}}_{\text{collisions}}$$

In this expression, the distribution function, f , has been replaced by the “phonon occupation number”, $n_{\mathbf{k},p}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, which tells us how many phonons are contained in a given vibrational mode, and:

- \mathbf{k} is the wave vector (spatial frequency), which could be written as $\mathbf{k}(\omega)$ to emphasize that there are multiple combinations of \mathbf{k} and ω ,
- p is the branch (acoustic, i.e. lowest frequency vibrations, or optical, i.e. higher frequency vibrations), and
- \mathbf{r} and t refer to position and time respectively

This phonon occupation number, $n_{\mathbf{k},p}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, says, “on average, at this location and time, how many phonons are in the vibrational mode labeled by (\mathbf{k}, p) ?”, modifying the original BTE to describe the transport of heat energy. This modified form of the BTE is called the “phonon-BTE”. Note that the momentum streaming and source term were omitted to simplify the description to a material conducting heat naturally with no driving force or heat source.

In summary, the phonon-BTE tracks how phonons are distributed and scattered, and thus provides a microscopic foundation for heat conduction.

Connection to the Fourier Heat Equation

Under a set of assumptions, the phonon-BTE collapses into the Fourier Heat Equation, demonstrating how the macroscopic law is an abstraction of a deeper reality. The assumptions that connect both equations are as follows:

- **Steady State:** We assume that *on average*, the phonon occupation number across all modes remains constant with time, that is, $\frac{\partial n_{\mathbf{k},p}}{\partial t} = 0$.
- **Near local equilibrium:** For a system in equilibrium, or a “balanced” state, the distribution of phonons across vibrational modes is said to follow something called the “Bose-Einstein distribution” – I find it fascinating that there is order to it. To collapse the phonon-BTE to Fourier’s Law, we assume that the distribution of phonons across modes only “slightly” deviates from the Bose-Einstein distribution.
- **Relaxation time approximation:** The collision term in the phonon-BTE accounts for phonon scattering events. In reality, these scattering processes are difficult to capture

exactly, since vibrational modes are constantly scattering and exchanging phonons (even though the distribution of $n_{k,p}$ across modes appears to be ordered [following the Bose-Einstein pattern] when at equilibrium and *zoomed out in time*). Hence, we approximate the collision term as the ratio between the deviation of $n_{k,p}$ from equilibrium and the “relaxation time”, which is the average time a phonon will travel before undergoing a scattering event.

- **Diffusive limit:** The “mean free path” is defined as the average distance a vibrational mode will travel before undergoing a scattering event (and is related to the relaxation time through something called the “group velocity”, defined as $v_{k,p} = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial k}$). For heat conduction to be diffusive, thus reducing the phonon-BTE to Fourier’s Law, we assume that the length scale of the material being investigated is much larger than the mean free path. For example, if we are studying heat conduction through a glass cup (made of fused silica, so high-purity glass), we can assume that Fourier’s Law holds for heat conduction since the size of the glass cup is several, several times larger than the mean free path of silica, which is just a few nanometers (Siemens et al. 2009).

If any of these assumptions break down, Fourier’s Law no longer accurately describes heat conduction. One such case is in the study of heat conduction at the nanoscale, such as in semiconductor components where the mean free path is comparable to the device size. In the analysis of such situations, the phonon-BTE may be abstracted as a completely different macroscopic law, such as the “Hydrodynamic Heat Equation” investigated in detail by Beardo et al. (Beardo et al. 2020):

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{q} + \kappa \nabla T = l^2 [\nabla^2 \mathbf{q} + \alpha \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q})]$$

Where \mathbf{q} is the heat flux, τ is the relaxation time, κ is the thermal conductivity, α is a dimensionless parameter, and l is a length scale term that describes the scale of the material being analyzed. This equation is described as the “Hydrodynamic” Heat Equation due to its similarity in structure to the Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equation, which describes the flow of incompressible fluids and can be derived from the general BTE. This shows that when assumptions shift, even our most “fundamental” laws are revealed not as absolutes, but as provisional frameworks.

Overall, this section shows how the Fourier Heat Equation, largely considered to be a very general descriptor of heat conduction, is a context-bound description of a deeper reality – one which can take a completely different form under different conditions.

Molecular Dynamics and Beyond

In the previous section, the vibration of atoms was abstracted as lattice waves driven by phonons. However, through a computational technique known as Molecular Dynamics (MD), it is possible to directly simulate the individual interactions between atoms.

This is typically done through something called an “interatomic potential”, an equation (or set of equations) describing how atoms interact with each other. One of the most basic and universal descriptions of atomic interactions is called the “Lennard-Jones” interatomic potential.

Figure 6: Lennard-Jones Interatomic Potential

In summary, this interatomic potential describes interactions between atoms, and says that any two atoms interacting with each other will try to use the minimum energy necessary to remain in equilibrium. To maintain this balance, every object, living and non-living, is made up of atoms constantly attracting and repulsing each other as they get too far and too close respectively – the lower the temperature of the material, the lower the extent of the vibrations. I find it poetic that the energy-induced dance of attraction and repulsion which causes atoms to vibrate – ultimately generating heat – mirrors the push and pull of human relationships, whether platonic, romantic, familial, or professional. As with the generation and transmission of heat, love discovers its rhythm in human relationships by searching for a balance between individual sovereignty (Descartes: “*I think, therefore I am*”) and communal relationship (Ubuntu: “*I am because we are*”).

Beyond the atom, scientific research continues to probe the probabilistic nature of reality through quantum mechanics. For example, Thomas Young’s double-slit experiment (Young 1802) revealed

that an electron – a subatomic particle – can manifest as either a particle or a wave depending on observation. As science continues to push the frontiers of understanding the physical world, I believe it is equally essential to deepen our understanding of love. As renowned mathematician Edward Frenkel reminds us in *Love and Math* (Frenkel 2013), mathematics itself can be experienced as an act of love – not merely a collection of formulas, but a hidden reality of beauty and truth awaiting discovery. In the same way, love invites us to look beneath the surface of laws and abstractions to encounter the deeper reality they signify. That is, just as scientific laws must evolve with new insights, so too must our theological and social understandings evolve as our capacity to love deepens. In the next section, we will explore several cases discussing the love behind the law, marking the transition from scientific inquiry to contemporary theological and social issues.

Discussing the Love Behind the Law

Matthew 22:21 (NKJV)

They said to Him, "Caesar's." And He said to them, "Render therefore to Caesar the things that are Caesar's, and to God the things that are God's."

In Matthew 22:21, Christ was asked whether or not his followers should follow the laws and pay taxes, intending to trap him for promoting ideas of love that threatened the empire and religious institutions. In a stunning reply, He asked that all those who follow him should “render to Caesar the things that are to Caesar’s, and to render to God (Love) the things that are God’s (Love’s)”. However, with knowledge of the extent of oppression the Jewish people faced under the Roman Empire, this statement could not have possibly been an endorsement of Roman cruelty that harmed His people. Instead, I see this as a reminder that laws are social contracts agreed upon within society, and that His disciples should respect these laws while also pursuing deeper growth in the understanding of love – *the principle that should underlie every law*. It follows that when society evolves in its capacity to love, its laws must also evolve, or else they cease to reflect the values of the people they are meant to protect. From Moses confronting Pharaoh to David refusing Saul’s unjust pursuit, and Esther risking her life for her people, scripture provides several instances where the faithful challenged systems of injustice. In this section, we will transition from scientific discussion to social issues, eventually discussing liberation theologies with love as the underlying foundation. To this end, we will discuss three perspectives: Black Liberation, Feminist/Womanist, and Queer theologies.

From Science to Love: Abstractions and the Deeper Meaning

The science of psychology could be understood as an attempt to abstract patterns in human emotion and experience with concrete language (“APA Dictionary of Psychology” 2018). However, as I argued earlier, one human emotion – love – is as difficult to define as it is to implement. Researchers across philosophy, psychology, and neuroscience alike have noted that love resists precise categorization, remaining a “multifaceted construct” that transcends any single definition (Sternberg 1986), (Fisher 2004). Nonetheless, psychology has been responsible for sweeping progress in emotional health and in understanding patterns of human behavior. For example, the Stanford Prison Experiment demonstrated how quickly ordinary individuals adapt to roles of domination or submission under social pressure (Zimbardo 1973). Similar dynamics are invoked to explain Stockholm Syndrome, the phenomenon where hostages form attachments to their captors as a survival strategy (Namnyak et al. 2008). In this section, we will first discuss how placebo can be understood as an abstraction of faith – or belief in the unknown – and then emphasize the difficulty of defining love, using obscenity laws as a metaphor.

Faith in Disguise: Placebo and Belief

Modern science has repeatedly shown that the placebo effect can produce measurable physiological changes, even when patients know they are receiving an inactive treatment. For example, a 2010 Harvard study on “open-label placebos” found that patients with irritable bowel syndrome experienced significant symptom relief even after being told the pills contained no active drug (Kaptchuk et al. 2010). In other words, the mere act of believing in healing – even while *knowing* the mechanism was “untrue” – generated real outcomes in the body. This raises a provocative question: is “placebo” simply a scientific abstraction for belief-based healing?

Faith, in its biblical sense, works in much the same way: a belief in something unseen, without empirical guarantee, that nonetheless shapes lived experience. Christ himself often suggested that it was not merely his power, but the belief of his followers that made them well. “*Your faith has made you well*” (Mark 5:34, NKJV) is a refrain that reframes healing as relational trust. This can be contrasted with Mark 6:5, where Christ was “unable” to perform miracles in His own hometown due to His people’s lack of faith.

This pattern of faith-based healing reaches back into the wilderness narrative: when Israel was plagued by venomous serpents, healing came not from medicine but by looking at a bronze serpent lifted on a pole (Numbers 21:8–9). That simple act of belief-directed vision produced measurable physical recovery. The same symbol – a serpent coiled around a staff – endures in modern pharmaceutical imagery, a reminder of how ancient belief, symbol, and healing remain intertwined. This imagery, also used in ancient Greece to symbolize healing (and was known as the “Rod of Asclepius”) is now currently on the logo of the World Health Organization (WHO).

Figure 7: Rod of Asclepius on WHO Logo

Importantly, noting the similarity between placebo and faith does not require claiming that symbols themselves contain intrinsic power. As Professor Annie Wilkinson has remarked (in her NPEP seminar *Anthro 391: Witches, Bots, and Trolls - Misinformation in Society*, Northwestern University), the truth of a statement and its effect on collective behavior must *both* be analyzed. A claim can be “untrue” in one sense, yet still alter behavior and produce material consequences – from health outcomes to political movements. Belief itself is thus an active force in shaping reality.

Seen in this light, faith and placebo may not be opposing categories but parallel descriptions of how love and trust generate outcomes in human life. “*You shall know the truth, and the truth shall make you free*” (John 8:32, NKJV) reminds us that freedom is not only about propositional accuracy, but about the liberating effects of objective reality.

Faith in Colonial Nigeria

The story of Christianity in West Africa illustrates this dynamic. Missionaries arrived with schools and hospitals, but also with coercion and domination. My own grandfather, Yekini Odufisan, was forcefully renamed “Albert” before being allowed formal education – an echo of the systemic barriers marginalized communities still face today. Such forced assimilation, rooted in power and control, is incompatible with love, which depends on trust.

Yet legend tells of Joseph Ayo Babalola, a Nigerian who glimpsed beneath the cruelty of domination to rediscover the message of love. He reportedly left his job with the British to spread the gospel. Tales of his character include one where, after being mugged, he ran after the thieves to give them extra money he had hidden, feeling guilty for deceiving them (ekimogundescendant 2018). His ministry drew crowds with a hand-rung bell and buckets of water used as healing

symbols – a localized “placebo” that nonetheless generated real outcomes of faith, healing, and communal renewal.

Whether or not every miracle story is factually true, the effects are undeniable: Nigeria today is one of the most religious nations on earth, and its clergy rank among the most globally influential. Here, as with Gandhi and Martin Luther King Jr.’s nonviolent campaigns, love – embodied in collective belief – played a central role in liberation.

Matthew 7:20, NKJV

“By their fruits you will know them”

Love, Law, and the Case of Obscenity

Earlier in this work, I argued that love is a term that resists precise definition. Here, I turn to the difficulty of using law to abstract love, with obscenity laws serving as a case study.

In Eden, Adam and Eve were *“both naked, the man and his wife, and were not ashamed”* (Genesis 2:25, NKJV). Their lack of clothing was not lawless but rather a natural expression of trust and mutual love. Yet when sin entered, shame appeared: *“the eyes of both of them were opened, and they knew that they were naked; and they sewed fig leaves together and made themselves coverings”* (Genesis 3:7, NKJV). This suggests that prohibitions or regulations around nudity are not about the human body itself, but about the distortions of love that produce lust, shame, fear, and objectification.

Modern nudism raises a similar question: is the law against public nudity an absolute moral truth, or simply a protective boundary in a world where love is fractured? In a society governed by true love, nakedness would not be scandalous, because every gaze would be reverent rather than exploitative. But in our present condition, laws against public nudity serve as boundaries – like grain boundaries in crystalline materials – that channel and protect love from distortion.

Paul writes: “[*They*] exchanged the truth of God for the lie, and worshiped and served the creature rather than the Creator” (Romans 1:25, NKJV). Lust mistakes the body – the creation, *formed from dust* (Genesis 2:7) – for the divine spark within, which was made in the image of the Creator. Thus, the love behind laws of modesty is not to deny the beauty of the body, but to protect it from being reduced to an object. The aim is not to abolish boundaries but to mature into a love that makes them unnecessary – returning, in a sense, to Eden, where nakedness was simply transparency and trust. Tragically, the plague of rape culture demonstrates how far we remain from that maturity, as many are still unable to observe beauty without attempting to consume it.

The difficulty of defining sexual content in law parallels the difficulty of defining love itself. In the landmark U.S. Supreme Court case *Jacobellis v. Ohio*, Justice Potter Stewart, when asked to define obscenity, confessed that he could not provide a precise definition of hardcore pornography but concluded, “I know it when I see it” (*Jacobellis v. Ohio* 1964). Love, I suggest, functions in a similar way: abstract definitions often fail, but when love is experienced in sustained and genuine form, it is universally recognizable. Even those shaped by distorted versions of love cannot help but recognize its truth when they are consistently shown it. A case could be made that the difficulty in describing love through words necessitated the incarnation of Christ, known in scripture as “The Word” (John 1:1), to demonstrate the true meaning of love.

Overall, this points to love as a deeper universal principle – indefinable in abstraction, undeniable in experience.

The Spirit Over the Letter: Love Behind Biblical Law

When confronted with the ghastly nature of certain commands in Leviticus, it is important to recognize the social conditions that rendered such laws necessary, and to reflect critically on the laws we ourselves endorse that may one day be judged with similar dismay. This section examines the love underlying biblical law, suggesting that even its harshest statutes were provisional attempts to safeguard life, trust, and community. In doing so, it prepares the ground for the discussion of liberation theology, where law and love converge in the pursuit of justice and freedom.

The Sabbath was Made for Man

Christ often *seemed* to contradict the law, and yet he also declared: “*Do not think that I came to destroy the Law or the Prophets. I did not come to destroy but to fulfill*” (Matthew 5:17, NKJV). Consider the episode where he allowed his disciples to pluck heads of grain on the Sabbath and later healed a lame man on the same day. The written word explicitly prohibited any kind of work on the Sabbath – including gathering or harvesting (see Numbers 15:32–36). By the letter of the law, his disciples’ actions could have been seen as direct disobedience. Yet Christ insisted: he was not abolishing the law, but *fulfilling* it.

How is this possible? The answer is that Christ was fulfilling the love behind the law. Reading the letters alone, it is easy to fall into a Pharisaical form of obedience: rigid, fearful, and unreflective.

But Christ revealed that the Sabbath was never meant to be a burden – it was a gift. As he put it: “The Sabbath was made for man, and not man for the Sabbath” (Mark 2:27, NKJV). The law was an abstraction of a deeper truth: that God intends for humanity to balance work and rest.

This is why Christ could heal and allow his disciples to eat on the Sabbath without abolishing the law. The love behind the law was not about enforcing inactivity, but about ensuring human flourishing. The Sabbath mirrors God’s own rest on the seventh day of creation (Genesis 2:2–3) – whether one interprets that “day” literally or allegorically, scripture underscores the sacred importance of rest, reflection, and communion with God.

Modern studies reinforce this ancient truth. Research on remote and flexible work demonstrates measurable improvements in well-being (Kesenheimer et al. 2025), and trials of the four-day work week show benefits in productivity, health, and quality of life (Henley Business School 2021). As humanity moves closer to an age of abundance, the biblical principle of Sabbath reminds us that flourishing requires not only work, but also rest, renewal, and love.

Where Your Treasure Is, There Your Heart Will Be Also

The idea behind animal sacrifices – discussed extensively in Leviticus (see Leviticus 1–7) – is that even the greatest wealth must be subservient to love. The sacrifice of one’s “best” symbolized devotion to God and service to community. Some Christian traditions continue this principle through the practice of tithing, which traces back to the Levites’ role in gathering a portion of Israel’s produce and wealth into the community storehouse (Numbers 18:21–24; Malachi 3:10). For those skeptical of institutional norms, the deeper principle remains: offering the best of what one has to serve the marginalized, the poor, and the needy is itself an act of love. Christ echoed

this when he taught, “*Assuredly, I say to you, inasmuch as you did it to one of the least of these My brethren, you did it to Me*” (Matthew 25:40, NKJV).

Freedom With Care

With the previous discussion in mind, the Christian faith could be said to define “sin” as anything out of line with love. Therefore, in attempting to abstract love through laws, I believe the conversation between conservatism and progressivism should not be focused on which side is “right.” Rather, such debates might be better imagined as a dance – releasing old scripts to uncover the deeper truth behind them, while carefully managing newfound freedom so that those who are not yet ready do not stumble into darkness. All conversations of this kind can be carried out in peace, so long as love remains at the center.

Romans 14:19, NKJV

“Therefore let us pursue the things which make for peace and the things by which one may edify another”

Liberation Theology: God (Love) is on the Side of the Oppressed (Psalm 9:9)

Psalm 9:9, NKJV

“The Lord also will be a refuge for the oppressed, a refuge in times of trouble”

Liberation theology is broadly defined as a theological movement that interprets the gospel of Jesus Christ through the lived experiences of the poor and oppressed, emphasizing God’s

preference for the poor (Gustavo 1988). At its heart, it insists that theology is not an abstract discipline but a living practice – a reflection on faith born out of action from a place of concern for others, as the Rev Dr. Martin Luther King Jr. preached in his sermon “*Why Jesus Called A Man A Fool*” – where he described a man who used the word “I” and “my” so often that he lost the capacity to say “we” and “our”. In this sermon, MLK Jr. emphasized that individual success and the wellbeing of the group are intertwined.

The Liberation Theology movement first gained prominence in Latin America in the late twentieth century as clergy and lay leaders responded to political repression, economic inequality, and systemic violence. It has since expanded into related traditions, including Black theology (Cone 1997) and womanist theology (Williams 1993). The scriptural quotation that opens this section affirms the conviction that God – that is, Love – is on the side of the oppressed. This reframes law, power, and even salvation in terms of liberation.

However, as history warns, the oppressed can just as easily become the oppressor when they stop trusting in the equilibrating power of love and begin to trust in tools of control and domination to force certain outcomes. Nonetheless, even in the darkest hours of any situation imaginable, love has been shown to biblically always find a way – the resurrection of Christ, which is the centerpiece of the Christian faith, is a parallel of love defeating our worst fear – death itself.

Romans 8:38–39 (NKJV)

*“For I am persuaded that **neither death nor life**, nor angels nor principalities nor powers, nor things present nor things to come, nor height nor depth, nor any other created thing, shall be able to separate us from the love of God which is in Christ Jesus our Lord.”*

This section investigates ideas of Liberation Theology across three contexts: Black Liberation, Feminist/Womanist, and Queer theology.

**Black Liberation Theology: Turning the Other Cheek as the Power of Love Over Empire
(Luke 23:24)**

Luke 23:34, NKJV

“Father, forgive them, for they do not know what they do.”

Recall the previous discussion on the placebo effect, where Joseph Ayo Babalola’s belief in the power of love was instrumental in awakening Nigeria to the confidence it brings in spite of any outcome. In contrast, fear leads only to self-preservation.

1 John 4:18, NKJV

“There is no fear in love; but perfect love casts out fear...”

Much earlier in this work, laws were defined as collective agreements on how best to preserve the survival of a group or society. Yet the fact that love does not use force does not imply passivity. On the contrary – love assumes that even the oppressor can be reasoned with.

Hebrews 5:14, NKJV

“But solid food belongs to those who are of full age, that is, those who by reason of use have their senses exercised to discern both good and evil.”

This is why I believe Christ, the Shepherd, referred to his followers as sheep. A ram's (male sheep) horns are capable of immense damage, but the sheep is often depicted as docile and unintelligent. Yet the immense physical strength of the ram suggests that it follows the Shepherd not because it is weak – any ram could easily impale the Shepherd – but because of complete trust. That trust is love. Even Christ as Shepherd of humanity referred to Himself not only as Teacher but also as Friend:

John 15:15, NKJV

“No longer do I call you servants... but I have called you friends, for all things that I heard from My Father I have made known to you.”

The posture of the sheep is one of honest, respectful exchange, rather than force. In the United States, oppressive structures were most powerfully challenged not by domination but by appeals to humanity – through arts, preaching, music, and media. Though it is completely undignified to have to prove one's right to exist, this faith in the conquering power of love produced some of the greatest cultural works of all time – from *ROOTS*, chronicling love's endurance through the horrors of the transatlantic slave trade, to Yoruba films such as *Şaworoidę* and *Agógó Ewò*, which are commentaries on class struggle. Oral traditions, music, and art – from Ebenezer Obey to Smokey Robinson, Hubert Ogunde to Bobby Womack, James Brown, and Bob Marley – have traditionally been the primary means for preserving African Philosophical thought, and have done much to advance society toward love in the face of darkness, including slavery's persistent legacies.

In light of this, “*turn the other cheek*” (Matthew 5:39, NKJV) must not be read as passivity but as an invitation into the costly, radical work of love. This commandment found its echo in the Civil

Rights and African Liberation movements, where music, preaching, and media softened hearts more effectively than brute force ever could. Yet scripture also affirms that force and love are not opposites. Christ overturned the tables in the temple not to frighten the money changers, but to reveal the fury within love. The plagues of Egypt likewise demonstrated that God's first movement is always gentle correction, until oppression makes forceful *reckoning* unavoidable. Even "Hell," described as fire, can be seen not as annihilation but as purification – restorative justice that strips away false identities until the truth of love is remembered and embraced.

Malachi 3:2, NKJV

"For He is like a refiner's fire and like launderers' soap."

This paradox of love was mirrored in Black America by Malcolm X and Martin Luther King Jr.: one embodying readiness to meet violence with force, the other embodying the transforming power of nonviolent love. Together they revealed that resistance requires both the knowledge of force and the deeper trust in love.

Therefore, when Jesus says "*turn the other cheek*" (Matthew 5:39, NKJV), or when Paul writes "*slaves, obey your masters*" (Ephesians 6:5, NIV), these cannot be reduced to subservience. Rather, they call for radical trust that forgiveness and love can break the cycle of domination more powerfully than retaliation. To forgive in the face of dehumanization is not to deny the reality of evil, but to refuse to let evil set the terms of the relationship.

As James Cone insisted in *God of the Oppressed*, love does not negate resistance – it transforms it (Cone 1997). And as liberation theologians across traditions remind us, God’s love always takes the side of the oppressed, yet never by mirroring the oppressor’s tools of domination.

Womanist/Feminist Theology: The Voices of the Margins are Prophets of Love (Luke 1:52-53)

Biblically, women could be said to be “Priestesses of Love” – one interpretation of Eve’s choice in Eden can be read as embodying a love so trusting that she assumed anything existing in Paradise must have good intentions. Whether the story of Eden is physical or allegorical is beside the point, in my opinion – it abstracts the principle of the fall from trust and love into fear and control. The “curses” laid out on departure from Eden read thus: to the man, Love said:

Genesis 3:17–19 (NKJV)

“Cursed is the ground for your sake;

In toil you shall eat of it

All the days of your life.

Both thorns and thistles it shall bring forth for you,

And you shall eat the herb of the field.

In the sweat of your face you shall eat bread

Till you return to the ground,

For out of it you were taken;

For dust you are,

And to dust you shall return.”

And to the woman:

Genesis 3:16 (NKJV)

"I will greatly multiply your sorrow and your conception;

In pain you shall bring forth children;

Your desire shall be for your husband,

And he shall rule over you."

For the man, these verses highlight the physical exertion necessary for survival – whether through hunting or gathering – and modern research confirms that sustained physical exhaustion negatively affects emotional health (Fan et al. 2023). For the woman, the “curse” is framed in relational terms: “*your desire shall be for your husband, and he shall rule over you*” (Genesis 3:16, NKJV). These verses reflect a division of labor that appears in many survival-oriented societies, where men more often undertook physically demanding tasks such as big-game hunting, while women frequently carried relational and communal responsibilities (Anderson et al. 2023). Importantly, this division is not an eternal prescription of men as physical and women as emotional, but rather a survival adaptation shaped by scarcity.

Overall, the text portrays *gender roles as a consequence of the fall*, not as God’s ideal: men’s strength directed toward protecting life, and women’s relational influence toward preserving it. Similar concepts of balancing complementary energies can also be found in Asian philosophy’s Yin (feminine) and Yang (masculine), which highlight interdependence rather than hierarchy. Yet in the modern world, survival is no longer determined by brute physical labor alone, nor is emotional labor confined to women. Therefore, this rigid gender split has become obsolete, leaving

space for both men and women – and indeed all people – to share in the full spectrum of physical and emotional strength.

While these interpretations are necessarily theological and metaphorical (and could be read as speculative), the Bible shows several women influencing the course of history – such as Esther, trusting in the power of love to risk her life to save her people. From Mọremí Àjásòrò to Joan d’Arc, women have been responsible for making crucial, risky decisions that have altered the course of history in the direction of love. Even Mary – in whom Christ was incarnated – happily accepted the risk of communal shame and rejection for her “unknown pregnancy” in service of love.

Luke 1:38 (NKJV)

“Behold the maidservant of the Lord! Let it be to me according to your word”

Even in other cultures, glimpses of this truth of women as Priestesses of Love can be found. In the Yorùbá language, *Olorì* means “queen,” and *Olóri* means “leader,” but the latter is actually a contraction of “*O l’ori*” – literally translated as “they own the head.” While words with similar spellings and different tones can have widely divergent meanings in Yorùbá, the closeness of these terms may suggest a shared etymological root, as Omoagbametala discusses in greater detail (OMOAGBAMETALA 2015). The paradox they capture is striking: the one who is supposedly “under” authority is also the one guiding the authority itself. Scripture echoes this mystery: *“Nevertheless, in the Lord woman is not independent of man, nor man of woman”* (1 Corinthians 11:11, NKJV). God’s wisdom is often subversive, reminding us that true leadership and true love are inseparable – not domination, but interdependence.

The game of chess offers another striking illustration. A game ends when the king is under checkmate, making him appear to be the most important piece on the board. Yet in reality, the king is the weakest, confined to moving a single square at a time. It is the queen who is the most powerful, able to move freely in any direction. In practice, the loss of a queen often signals defeat, since even a moderately skilled player can usually convert that advantage into victory. This paradox mirrors the dynamic of human relationships: the figure recognized as “head” may symbolize authority, but true strength and vitality are often carried by the one considered subordinate. In God’s design, both roles reveal their dependence on each other (1 Corinthians 11:11), pointing us back to mutuality rather than domination. Therefore work in a biblically defined marriage is to improve the other’s skills in those where they are lacking, as both emotional and physical strength are components needed for love and survival respectively.

Ephesians 5:33

*“Nevertheless let each one of you in particular so **love** his own wife as himself, and let the wife see that she **respects** her husband.”*

In summary, contentious verses like “*be quiet*” (1 Timothy 2:11–12) may have been a call for, less survival-equipped “women” in ancient societies to express respect for the mental, physical, and emotional effort required to control survival outcomes. Meanwhile, other verses such as Ephesians 5:21 and Ephesians 5:33 could be calls for the less emotionally-equipped “men” to acknowledge and love the mental, physical, and emotional effort required to maintain emotional stability. However, in our modern age of abundance, where physical exertion is not needed to earn income for survival, these rigid gender roles simply do not hold any longer. How blessed, then, are our

queer brethren, many of whom already have the skills to switch effortlessly between the two?! This sets up the next and concluding discussion section diving into Queer theology.

Queer Theology: Breaking Boundaries to Reveal the Boundless Love of God (Galatians 3:28)

Galatians 3:28, NKJV

*“There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free, there is **neither male nor female**; for you are all one in Christ Jesus.”*

In the previous section, I suggested that the ability to switch effortlessly between physical and emotional survival skills is a property of queerness. It follows that in an age of abundance – where less physical exertion is necessary (no longer “*toiling the soil*” for survival, Genesis 3:17-19) – those born biologically female may increasingly earn income (though, unfortunately, the gender pay gap and unequal access to education remain), and those born biologically male may find enough physical comfort to explore their emotional health. This aligns with the biblical vision that in Christ – the human expression of Love – gender distinctions lose their ultimate authority. Gender is, instead, an internal construct built upon the “self,” the *Imago Dei*, the image of God (Love).

Genesis 1:26, NKJV

“Then God said, ‘Let Us make man in Our image, according to Our likeness...’”

In our age of modern comforts, the structure of the physical body no longer needs to be rigidly bound to the internal self. A combination of natural propensity, personal choice, and external factors (including early childhood experiences) may result in what appears to be a mismatch

between the self and the body. Gender studies scholars have explored this at length (Butler 1990), and the biblical vision of the body as a temple reinforces the point: the body contains the image of Love, and identity may be built upon it in diverse ways – as long as it is aligned with love.

Therefore, as with modifications to temple structures for accessibility, or modifications to the bodies of the physically disabled, the discussion around transgender identities should not center on “permission” to renovate the temple of the body. Rather, the focus must be on how such renovations are guided by love. The body is sacred – and like any temple, care must be taken to ensure that changes align with the truth of the indwelling self, enabling a person to live more fully and to love more deeply. Loving regulation, therefore, should not be about prohibition but protection: ensuring that changes foster flourishing rather than harm. This requires discernment in cases of vulnerability or limited rational capacity (such as age), where love – not fear or recklessness – must remain the guiding principle.

When it comes to romantic partnerships, hints of queer inclusion appear even in Genesis, where the English Standard Version (ESV) preserves a notable distinction from the original Hebrew text:

Genesis 7:2–3, ESV

*“Take with you seven pairs of all clean animals, the **male and his mate**, and a pair of the animals that are not clean, the **male and his mate**; and seven pairs of the birds of the heavens also, **male and female**, to keep their offspring alive on the face of all the earth.”*

Here the text distinguishes between pairing “male and female” (for procreation) and “the male and his mate” (for companionship). The implication is that while procreation may be one reason for

partnership, it is not the only one. A person of any internal gender – even while inhabiting a “male temple” in this example – may choose a partner of any internal gender for the purpose of growing together in love.

Thus, following the earlier discussion on lust, the sin of Romans 1:25 is not the existence of queer relationships, but the distortion of love itself:

Romans 1:25, NKJV

*“...who exchanged the truth of God for the lie, and worshiped and served the **creature** rather than the **Creator**, who is blessed forever. Amen.”*

In ancient Rome, soldiers and men with power frequently used their status to sexually exploit people of all genders (Ruden 2011). This was domination, not love. In contrast, queer relationships today – freely chosen and rooted in mutual trust – embody Eden’s original intention: to balance physical and emotional survival skills, to grow together in love, and to reflect the boundless image of God.

Conclusions and Implications on Everyday Life

This work has traced a single thread through science, law, and scripture: what we call “laws” are context-bound abstractions of deeper realities. In physics, Fourier’s law governs heat at one scale, yet yields to the phonon-BTE or hydrodynamic forms at another – reminding us that formulas are provisional frames for something more fundamental. In society, legal codes are negotiated compacts meant to safeguard communal life – never ends in themselves. In scripture, commandments point beyond their letters to a living center: love.

A helpful material analogy emerged along the way. Thermal conductivity, the measure of efficient heat conduction, depends on a material’s capacity to hold energy, to conduct it efficiently, and to channel it through structure. Human beings, likewise, carry different “capacities” for love, convey it with varying skill, and rely on healthy structures to guide its flow. In materials, grain boundaries can impede or shape heat flow (Zhang et al. 2022); in relationships, wise boundaries protect love from distortion.

Figure 8: High Angle vs Low Angle Grain Boundaries (“A Review Article on Stabilizing Nanostructures in Metals----Institute of Metal Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences” 2013)

Scripture's own pattern confirms this. Sabbath law yields to the love behind it – human flourishing through rest and renewal. Sacrificial systems yield to the love beneath them – generosity for the poor and the “least of these”. Liberation theologies read God's preferential care for the oppressed as love's public face. Womanist and feminist lenses reveal love's interdependent wisdom. Queer theology names love's freedom to unite persons in mutuality. In each case, the Spirit animates the letter – not by abolishing it, but by fulfilling its aim.

Earlier, we suggested that this parallel between heat conduction and love could help explain why scripture describes hell as a refiner's fire. As Paul wrote:

1 Corinthians 3:12–13, NKJV

“Now if anyone builds on this foundation with gold, silver, precious stones, wood, hay, straw, each one's work will become clear; for the Day will declare it, because it will be revealed by fire; and the fire will test each one's work, of what sort it is.”

Our lifetime, then, could be viewed as a privilege to build constructs upon the eternal foundation of Love, with only the identity constructs in honest alignment with love surviving eternally.

Overall, the practical implication is clear: we were created to love. Our calling is to stretch human creativity to its limits in discovering new ways to express this eternal reality toward God and one another. And in the end, “*every knee shall bow*” (Philippians 2:10, NKJV) – not out of fear or coercion, but in awe of the power of Love.

It is my hope, prayer, and conviction that when every person finally surrenders to Love, allowing this indescribable truth to govern every choice, the world itself will be restored to Eden.

In Jesus Name,

Amen.

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